

DPU Dr. D. Y. Patil
B-School

(Program Approved by AICTE, Ministry of Education, Govt. of India)

Presents

CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

of International Conference on

**Fostering Resilient Business
Ecosystems and Economic
Growth: Towards the Next Normal**

(April 27 to 29, 2022)

Editors

Dr. Amol Gawande

Dr. Atul Kumar

Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School

Tathawade, Mumbai Bangalore Highway

Pune 411033, Maharashtra, India

DOES NET NEUTRALITY HAVE ANY EFFECT ON THE INDIAN INTERNET USERS? AN EMPIRICAL STUDY

Atul Kumar, Chirag Garg, Vikas Kumar

Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School

E mail: vikas.kumar.dypbs@gmail.com

Abstract:

Regarded as Open Internet Order, earlier, Net neutrality is based on the notion of how fairly is it used i.e. there should be no blocking, throttling or paid prioritization. This facility makes sure that the traffic is operated on fairly on the basis of content and not the origin. This study is based on understanding the impact of net neutrality and on the Indian internet users.

This research aims to assess the ability of net neutrality to maintain continuous internet speed and random locations of Mumbai. To find out the common notion of 4G users regarding the affordability of data services and to assess browsing experience of Indians and how does Net Neutrality impact this experience.

In the study a consistent internet speed across various Indian Telecom operators after the implementation of net neutrality was found. Internet users expressed their agreeableness on the affordability and quality of the browsing experience of 4G service.

Keywords: *Net Neutrality, Open Internet Order, internet Users in India, 4G data services*

1. Introduction:

Transparency and no discrimination are the main pillars of Net Neutrality. This implies that all the internet service providers are bound to operate on the same lines for all the websites w.r.t speed, cost or data. They are not authorised to stop or paly with the content of the website else they would have to face legal consequences. Apart from legal compliances, the transparency of this process was also required to check whether there is partiality when it comes to charging the subscribers.

This study aims at exploring how the net neutrality impact the Indian internet users. The study was done at random locations in Mumbai. The study also involved assessing the affordability of 4G data services and the impact of net neutrality on the browsing experience.

2. Research Method:

Responses from 240 internet users in Mumbai were collected using convenience sampling. 80 responses from 3 major telecom players' users namely- Reliance Jio, Bharti Airtel and Vodaphone idea was taken. The questionnaire was designed on the 5 point Likert Scale and validated to measure the impact of Net neutrality on the following stated variables:- Internet speed, Affordability and Overall browsing

experience. The questionnaire was tested for validity. The results were thus analysed to draw the conclusion.

3. Hypothesis:

H1: There is significant relationship between the net neutrality and the consistency of internet speed across different Indian telecom operators.

H2: Net Neutrality has a positive correlation with internet browsing experience.

H3: 4G services are still affordable post application of Net Neutrality.

4. Data analysis and Results:

The constructs- Internet speeds of different data service providers, internet browsing experience and the affordability of 4G data services. The questionnaire was designed and the responses were collected on 5 point Likert scale. One sample T test was used to compare actual mean and hypothesized mean with alpha level of 0.01. Cronbach alpha score was 0.891 which validated the reliability of the questionnaire. From the responses collected, the average age of the respondents was 27.01 with a std. deviation of 1.93 which signifies that most of the respondents were youngsters who mostly use internet services for most of the online activities. For the T test result it was found that assumed mean and actual mean are non-different ($p > 0.05$) which means that good internet browsing experience was seen after the implementation of net neutrality and the 4G services are still affordable.

5. Conclusion:

Internet fast lanes were replaced by net neutrality to speed up the browsing experience. Net neutrality has given all consumers equal access to information on the Internet. This has played an important role in transition from broadcast television to digital television. Broadcasters face greater challenges when trying to deliver content on new platforms. The first and most important argument against increasing net neutrality is the potential impact on underprivileged people who do not have access to modern technology. As of 2016, India's internet penetration rate is about 33%. Those who do not yet have a phone and those who live in remote areas without broadband access

References:

1. American Association of Community Colleges and others <http://www.arl.org/storage/documents/publications/higher-ed-libraries-net-neutrality-principles-10July2014.pdf>, July 10, 2014, Accessed on 05 Dec 2015
2. Ammori, M. (2009). Strange Bedfellows: Network Neutrality's Unifying Influence. *Regent UL Rev.*, 22, 335.
3. Cheng, H. K., Bandyopadhyay, S., & Guo, H. (2011). The debate on net neutrality: A policy perspective. *Information Systems Research*, 22(1), 60-82.
4. Dasgupta, D., & Roy, P. CHALLENGE BEFORE INDIAN NEW MEDIA: ASPIRATION FOR NETWORK NEUTRALITY-A STUDY OF NALGONDA DISTRICT.
5. Economides, N. (2007, August). Net Neutrality, Non-Discrimination and Digital Distribution of Content Through the Internet. TPRC.

6. Frieden, R. (2007). Network neutrality and its potential impact on next generation networks. Available at SSRN 1026635.
http://www.firstpost.com/ebook_download.php?id=338, 2012
7. Khedekar Naina, "What is net neutrality and why it is important in India", <http://tech.firstpost.com>, 13 Apr 2015, 08:53, Access on 12 Dec 2015.
8. Marsden, C. T. (2016). Comparative case studies in implementing net neutrality: A critical analysis of zero rating. Scripted, 13, 1.
9. NASSCOM (April 2015), Response to TRAI Consultation Paper on Regulatory Framework for OTT Players
10. Owen, B. M. (2007). The Net Neutrality Debate: Twenty Five Years after United States v. AT&T and 120 Years after the Act to Regulate Commerce.
11. Prasad, R. (2018). Ascendant India, digital India: how net neutrality advocates defeated Facebook's Free Basics. *Media, culture & society*, 40(3), 415-431.
12. Sharma, A. K., Bajpai, B., Adhvaryu, R., Pankajkumar, S. D., Gordhanbhai, P. P., & Kumar, A. (2021). An Efficient Approach of Product Recommendation System using NLP Technique. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, Article in Press, Available online 6 August 2021. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2021.07.371>
13. Shahin, S. (2019). Facing up to Facebook: How digital activism, independent regulation, and mass media foiled a neoliberal threat to net neutrality. *Information, communication & society*, 22(1), 1-17.

ABOUT THE CONFERENCE

“Next Normal” is the latest buzzword two years after the Covid -19 pandemic hit all the sections of society and the economy. With the havoc now seemingly showing the downturn, it's the “Next to Normal” that will define 2022 and the subsequent years. Covid-19 has changed the world, society, and business function. With the Next Normal, the future demands resilience. Resilience is the CEO agenda of every company and across all industries. Businesses are reconsidering their approaching order to make it more resilient. Re-evaluating one's supply base, geographical footprint, moving with speed to digitize the operations end to end, encouraging flexibility to create new value for the customers, and increasing competitive advantage are certain considerations that need to be undertaken to build a resilient ecosystem for economic growth in the Next Normal. The 'Next Normal' also calls for innovative ways to re-engage an organization's human resources and marketing techniques. Other measures such as financial assistance, devising a favorable environment for the growth of startups, and regional collaboration among ecosystem developers can play an essential role in transforming the way businesses work are the other factors business leaders should consider as they prepare for “The Next Normal.” There is a need for in-depth scientific reflection regarding the methods and instruments for economic development in theoretical and practical terms. In this background, the prime goal of this Conference is to be a platform for discussing scientific achievements and evaluate the current state of research development on the role of institutional, financial, and technological innovation in fostering a resilient business ecosystem and economic growth.

ABOUT US

Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School runs AICTE approved PGDM program. It has been ranked 1st Emerging B-School among top institutes of west India by Times of India. It has also been conferred the ET Now Business School of the Year award. The two-year full-time PGDM program offered by Dr. D.Y. Patil B-School is designed to empower students to become successful business professionals in the challenging global scenario. The Institute is continually evolving to meet its goals in an ever-changing business environment. It has been playing an important role in professionalizing Indian management through its programs. Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School aims to create value-driven leaders, global managers and entrepreneurs with strong conceptual foundations and analytical approach to help them be the best in whichever field they choose. The aim is to innovatively address the needs of a modern India and connecting aspirations and realities to attain benchmarks that are respected internationally.

Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School

Sr. No. 87-88, Bengaluru-Mumbai Express Bypass,
Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra, India

Contact No. : 8007989201

Email : info.bschool@dpu.edu.in

Website : www.bschool.dpu.edu.in